

Giant Bilateral Hernia: A Case Report

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Abstract

This case report describes the management of a rare and complex case of obstructed bilateral giant inguinal hernias in a 55-year-old male. The patient had a history of right inguinal hernia surgery 11 years prior, and presented to the emergency room with symptoms of small bowel obstruction due to the presence of large, non-reducible left and reducible right inguinal hernias extending to mid-thigh. Imaging revealed a strangulated left hernia containing a portion of the jejunum and sigmoid colon, while the right hernia involved the cecum, terminal ileum, and other bowel structures.

The patient underwent emergency bilateral inguinal surgery with a careful focus on monitoring for abdominal compartment syndrome. The Trendelenburg position was used to aid the reduction of herniated contents, and both hernia sacs were excised, with a tissue-based repair using the Bassini technique. Postoperatively, the patient had an uneventful recovery, with no complications or recurrence noted at the 3-month follow-up, though excess scrotal skin remained, which might require future management.

Introduction

Inguinal hernia is defined as a protrusion of abdominal content into the inguinal canal, resulting from a defect or weakness in the abdominal wall. It is among the most common surgical conditions in the general population particularly affecting men [1].

A giant inguinal hernia is relatively rare and presents significant challenges in surgical management. It is characterized by an inguinal hernia that extends below the midpoint of the inner thigh when the patient is standing [2,3]. It is often associated with neglect and problem denial and results in difficulties in daily activities and therefore a reduced quality of life [4].

This case report presents the management of a rare presentation of obstructed bilateral giant inguinal hernias in a 55-year-old male patient. The article discusses the diagnostic approach, the surgical management of such advanced hernias, and the postoperative outcomes, with a focus on the challenges faced during the intervention and the long-term follow-up.

More Information

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Presentation of the Case

A 55-year-old male, who underwent a non-mesh tissue repair for a right inguinal hernia 11 years ago, presented to the emergency room with a huge obstructed bilateral inguinal hernia with associated symptoms of small bowel obstruction. The bilateral swelling was gradually enlarging for the past 11 years. On examination he had a giant non-reducible left inguinal hernia and a reducible right inguinal hernia both extending to the level of mid-thigh (figure 1).

CT scan of the abdomen and pelvis revealed a small bowel obstruction with a strangulated giant left inguinal hernia, containing a large portion of the jejunum, fluid, and the sigmoid colon. The right inguinal hernia contained the cecum, terminal ileum, and fluid accumulation (figure 2).

Figure 1: Gross Appearance of Bilateral Giant Inguinal Hernia

Figure 2: CT (Axial View) Demonstrating Large Bilateral Inguinal Hernia Sac Containing Bowel and Fluid

Emergency bilateral inguinal surgery was carried out with a bilateral inguinal incision. During the procedure, the patient's peak airway pressure was continuously monitored to assess for abdominal compartment syndrome, and the pressures remained within normal

limits. The left hernia sac was opened, and the spermatic cord was dissected and protected. The left hernia contained 1 meter of viable small bowel, and the sigmoid colon, 1 liter of fluid was evacuated (figure 3).

Figure 3: Content of Left Hernia Sac (After Partial Reduction of Small Bowel and Evacuation of Fluid)

Figure 4: Content of Right Hernia Sac

Given the reduced abdominal cavity volume and the chronicity of the herniation, the Trendelenburg position was used to facilitate the reduction of the

herniated contents. The hernia sac was excised at the level of the internal ring and ligated using a non-absorbable suture and a tissue based repair was performed using the Bassini technique.

We proceeded then to treating the right hernia using the same method, the hernia sac contained the terminal ileum, appendix, cecum, ascending and transverse colon, and most of the greater omentum (figure 4).

The patient made an uneventful recovery post-operatively, with no complications, and was discharged home on postoperative day 7, figure 5 shows the final closure. While the patient showed no signs of recurrence during the 3-month follow-up, excess scrotal skin remains, which may require further evaluation and possible management.

Discussion

Giant inguinal hernia is found exclusively in males and is significantly more complex and difficult to treat compared to regular inguinal hernias. The complication rate is high, with literature reviews indicating a 40% complication rate in patients undergoing surgery for giant inguinal hernia. Historically, there have been reports of deaths due to the sudden and significant increase in intra-abdominal pressure when returning the herniated organs, which had been outside the abdominal cavity for a long time, back into the cavity, leading to respiratory failure. In 2014, a classification system for giant inguinal hernia has been developed,

this system divides the disease into three types based on the size of the hernia sac and proposes corresponding treatment methods (figure 6) [5].

Figure 5: Post-Operative Closure of Hernia

Figure 6: Classification System for Giant Inguinal Hernia by Siriraj

The case of a 55-year-old male presenting with obstructed type II bilateral giant inguinal hernias highlights significant surgical challenge, the massive size of the hernias in this case presents the risk of intra-abdominal hypertension and the difficulty of achieving a tension-free repair.

Abdominal compartment syndrome (ACS) is a clinical manifestation of increased pressure within the abdominal cavity, usually beginning with intra-abdominal hypertension (IAH). It occurs when the pressure in the abdominal cavity rises above 20 mmHg and causes end-organ damage [6].

In this case, careful attention was paid to maintaining normal peak airway pressure, as well as the use of the Trendelenburg position, aspiration of peritoneal fluid (a total of 1,2 Liter) from the hernia sac to facilitate the reduction of the herniated bowel contents.

This case also demonstrates the importance of monitoring the patient closely for signs of abdominal compartment syndrome, particularly in cases with large hernias. Despite the potential risks, the patient's recovery was uneventful, and there were no signs of postoperative complications or recurrence at the 3-month follow-up.

Conclusion

This case underscores the importance of individualized care in patients with giant inguinal hernias and the need for ongoing monitoring in the postoperative period to manage complications. Moreover, it illustrates the utility of classification systems in guiding surgical decisions for giant inguinal hernias, ultimately improving patient outcomes. The successful outcome of this case emphasizes the value of a multidisciplinary approach to managing complex hernias, ensuring optimal surgical results and long-term patient quality of life.

Provenance and Peer Review

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Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflicts Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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